

Table 1. Performance of Zhongyu 87-1 in late season hybrid rice demonstration test.^a Zhejiang, China, 1988.

Location	Height (m)	Panicles/hill (no.)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Sterility (%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase over Shanyou 6 (%)
Quxian	78.7	9.7	99.3	10.6	29.4	7.1	14.8
Huangyan	81.0	10.3	105.7	13.6	30.8	7.5	5.0
Fuying	83.8	10.4	112.6	12.0	27.8	8.8	42.0
Shuichang	75.1	10.9	91.9	23.1	26.9	5.1	-3.5
Wenlin	-	11.3	116.1	9.7	26.1	8.3	14.3
Leqing	-	12.0	111.6	15.4	27.5	7.4	2.2

^aPlot size = 133 m².

lodging resistance. Panicles are large (106-110 grains/panicle) and grain-filling rate high (85%), with 27-29 g/1,000 grains and 22-23% amylose content. In 1989, Zhongyu 87-1 was promoted to regional adaptability tests in Hubei and Zhejiang. □

Table 2. Yield of Zhongyu 87-1 in midseason rice preliminary regional adaptability tests. Hubei, China, 1988.

Location	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Increase over Quichao 2 (%)	Rank in test ^b
Wuhan	7.1**	16.5	1
Dongxihu	9.6**	11.6	2
Jinzhou	8.5**	17.3	1

^aOf 11 varieties. ** = significant at P = 0.01.

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Data management and computer modeling

Simulation of yield potential in rice cultivars

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We raised six lowland rice cultivars available from the gene bank of the Paddy Breeding Station, TNAU, Coimbatore, during 1988 wet season and conducted productivity studies. Yield potentials were computer simulated using the MACROS. L1D simulation model developed by IRRI.

Calculated and measured main yield of rice cultivars at Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

Cultivar	Calculated grain yield (t/ha)	Measured grain yield (t/ha)	Simulation percentage
ADT36	6.8	6.2	91.2
ADT37	5.1	4.8	94.1
CO 37	7.2	7.0	97.2
ASD16	5.2	5.1	98.1
TKM6	2.3	3.1	134.8
IR66	4.1	5.6	136.6

The program took into account dry matter accumulation, physiological characteristics, and weather prevailing during the growth period.

Observed and calculated grain yield are presented in the table. Measured grain yields within 10% ±100% of calculated grain yield are presented in the figure.

Calculated grain yield and measured yield agree satisfactorily in ADT36, ADT37, CO 37, and ASD16.

This shows that yield potential and production can be reasonably estimated on the basis of cultivar physiological characteristics and growing area weather conditions. □

Calculated and measured grain yield for rice cultivars. Coimbatore, India.

Seed technology

Screening rice varieties for grain dormancy

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Harvest of the second (Feb-Jun) crop at Kuttanad usually coincides with the rainy season. Popular high-yielding varieties grown during the second season lack seed dormancy and considerable loss occurs due to grain sprouting in the field.

We screened germplasm at RRS Moncompu for grain dormancy to